

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ID:.....	2
EXPERIMENT NO:	2
EXPERIMENT NAME :	2
OBJECTIVE:	2
THEORY :	2
DATA TABLE.....	6
CALCULATION:.....	6
RERSULT:.....	7
DISCUSSION:.....	8

TABLE OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1 : SEISMIC SURVEY TOOLS	2
FIGURE 2: SEISMIC REFLECTION DATA	2
FIGURE 3: REFRACTED & REFLECETED WAVES DURING SURVEY.....	3
FIGURE 4: CROSS-SECTION VIEW OF GEOPHONE & HYDROPHON.....	3
FIGURE 5: VISUALIZED OF TWT VS DEPTH	4
FIGURE 6: ANALYTICAL GRAPH	4
FIGURE 7: VELOCITY AT TOP & BOTTOM LAYER OF SUBSURFACE.....	5
FIGURE 8 : DESIRED TIME VS DISTANCE GRAPH & THICKNESS.....	8

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1 : THE VALUES OF THE TIME VS DISTANCE POINTS OF SEISMIC SURVEY...6	
TABLE 2: FINAL OUTCOMES OF THE ELEMENTS.....	7

ID: 202434010

EXPERIMENT NO.: 1

EXPERIMENT NAME: Analysis of Two-Way Time in Seismic Survey Interpretation.

OBJECTIVE:

- To understand the concept of two-way travel time (TWT) of seismic waves as they travel from the surface to a subsurface reflector and return to the receiver.
- To calculate the two-way travel time using seismic survey data and analyze its relationship with depth and subsurface layering.
- To observe how variations in seismic velocity affect two-way time and how TWT is used in identifying horizons and estimating subsurface depth.

THEORY:

Seismic surveys are one of the most important geophysical methods used to study what lies beneath reflections from different rock layers are recorded. When these waves travel through rocks containing hydrocarbons (oil or gas) they behave differently-the reflections become stronger or weaker depending on the fluid type and rock properties. Because of this reaction seismic data helps identify horizons, measure their depth and understand where potential hydrocarbon zones may exist.

FIGURE 1:SEISMIC SURVEY TOOLS

FIGURE 2: SEISMIC REFLECTION DATA

When seismic waves travel through the Earth, they encounter boundaries between layers with different physical properties. At these boundaries, part of the wave energy is reflected back toward the surface as reflected waves which help in imaging subsurface layers. Another part of the energy bends and travels along the boundary between layers with different velocities as refracted waves, eventually returning to the surface. Reflected waves are mainly used to identify horizons and structures while refracted waves provide information about the velocity and composition of subsurface materials.

FIGURE 3: REFRACTED & REFLECTED WAVES DURING SURVEY

A geophone and a hydrophone are seismic sensors that record seismic waves. A geophone, used on land, detects ground vibrations via electromagnetic induction, while a hydrophone used in water detects pressure changes using a piezoelectric element. Both record seismic energy but differ in medium and working principle.

FIGURE 4: CROSS-SECTION VIEW OF GEOPHONE & HYDROPHONE

Two-Way Travel Time (TWT) is the total time a seismic wave takes to travel from the source to a subsurface layer and back to the surface. Geophones (on land) and hydrophones (in water) detect the reflected seismic waves and convert them into electrical signals. By measuring the time between wave generation and reception the TWT is recorded. Using this TWT and the known or estimated seismic velocity of the subsurface the depth of the reflecting layer can be calculated using the formula $d = \frac{v \times \text{TWT}}{2}$, where v is the seismic wave velocity. Accurate detection of reflected waves by these sensors is essential for determining the depth and structure of subsurface layers.

FIGURE 5: VISUALIZED OF TWT VS DEPTH

FIGURE 6: ANALYTICAL GRAPH

Seismic surveys also help to identify the thickness of subsurface layers and the formula $h = \frac{t v_1 v_2}{2\sqrt{v_2^2 - v_1^2}}$ is used to calculate the depth of a boundary between two layers using refracted seismic waves. When seismic waves travel through layers with different velocities (v_1 in the top layer and v_2 in the lower layer), part of the wave is refracted along the interface at the critical angle. Geophones or hydrophones detect these refracted waves and record the travel time t . Using this

recorded time and the known velocities of the layers the depth h can be calculated. The numerator tv_1v_2 comes from combining the travel time and layer velocities, while the denominator $2\sqrt{v_2^2 - v_1^2}$ comes from the geometry of the ray path at the critical angle. This links the measured seismic data with the actual depth and thickness of the subsurface boundary.

FIGURE 7: VELOCITY AT TOP & BOTTOM LAYER OF SUBSURFACE DEPOSIT THICKNESS

In a travel-time vs distance graph, straight-line segments represent waves traveling through layers at constant velocity, and changes in slope indicate layer boundaries. The slope of a segment ($\Delta t/\Delta x$) is inversely related to velocity, so the layer velocity can be calculated as $v = \Delta x/\Delta t$; steeper slopes indicate slower velocities while gentler slopes indicate faster velocities. Here, distance on the x-axis represents the horizontal separation between the seismic source and the geophone or hydrophone where the wave is recorded showing how far the seismic wave has traveled along the surface before being detected.

DATA TABLE:

DISTANCE(m)	TIME (ms)
5	14
15	23
25	30
35	36.75
45	42
55	50
65	54.5
75	61
85	65.5
95	66.5
105	70
115	73.25

Table 1 : The values of the Time vs Distance points of seismic survey

Plot the travel time curve and estimate the velocity & thickness of the first two layers (in m/s).

CALCULATION:

The slope of the first line is calculated as,

$$m_1 = \frac{(37 - 23) \times 10^{-3}}{35 - 15} = 7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s/m}$$

Hence, the velocity of the first layer is

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{m_1} = 1428.57 \text{ m/s}$$

The slope of the second line is calculated as,

$$m_2 = \frac{(66 - 55) \times 10^{-3}}{85 - 65} = 5.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s/m}$$

Hence, the velocity of the second layer is,

$$V_2 = \frac{1}{m_2} = 1818.18 \text{ m/s}$$

The straight-line equation for the refracted wave is,

$$t = m_2x + t_1$$

$$23 \times 10^{-3} = (7 \times 10^{-4} \times 15) + t_1$$

$$23 \times 10^{-3} = 10.5 \times 10^{-3} + t_1$$

$$t_1 = 0.0123 \text{ s}$$

The thickness of the first layer is calculated using,

$$h = \frac{t_1 V_1 V_2}{2\sqrt{V_2^2 - V_1^2}}$$

$$h = \frac{0.0125 \times 1428.57 \times 1818.18}{2\sqrt{1818.18^2 - 1428.57^2}}$$

$$h = 14.40 \text{ m}$$

RESULT:

From the above steps the value of thickness is found to be 14.40 m. Along with it, there are other values also found.

ELEMENTS	VALUES
Velocity in top layers (V1)	1428.57 m/s
Velocity in bottom layers(V2)	1818.18 m/s
Refracted waves travel time t_1	0.0123 s
Thickness of the subsurface layers (h)	14.40 m

Table 2: Final outcomes of the elements

FIGURE 8: DESIRED TIME VS DISTANCE GRAPH & THICKNESS

DISCUSSION:

The time vs distance graph represents the travel time of seismic waves as a function of the distance between the source and the receiver. The slope of the graph gives the velocity of the seismic waves in each layer which helps identify different subsurface layers. The top layer velocity, $V_1 = 1428.57 \text{ m/s}$, is relatively low, indicating that this layer consists of softer or less compact material such as soil or loose sediments. In contrast, the bottom layer velocity, $V_2 = 1818.18 \text{ m/s}$, is higher showing a denser and more compact material like rock or consolidated sediments. The difference in velocities causes reflection and refraction at the layer boundaries, which is essential for detecting subsurface structures. The intercept time $t_1 = 0.0125 \text{ s}$ is the travel time of seismic waves at zero source-receiver distance. Its value indicates the initial travel delay through the top layer and helps calculate the layer's thickness. Using t_1 along with V_1 & V_2 , the thickness of the top layer $h = 14.40 \text{ m}$, was determined. This thickness shows how deep the first layer extends before reaching the denser bottom layer. Seismic surveys are important because they allow non-destructive investigation of subsurface structures. Historically, they were used for locating water, minerals and hydrocarbon exploration. They provide reliable information about the Earth's subsurface without excavation.